

Fluorescence Characteristics of Tylophorinidine : Effect of pH and Buffer Molarity

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The fluorescence characteristics of tylophorinidine were examined in methanol, water and in increasing molarity of buffer at varying pH, 5-9.

In methanol the fluorescence spectra were closely similar to the excitation spectra. The fluorescence maximum was observed at 380 nm with a second band at 365 nm and a shoulder at 400 nm. These characteristic features were retained when the solvent was changed from methanol to water except that fluorescence maximum was shifted to longer wavelength by 5 nm.

In phosphate buffer of varying pH, 5-9, tylophorinidine fluoresced maximally at pH 5.0. However, fluorescence emission decreased with increasing pH. There was no alteration in the spectral pattern in this pH range which remained the same as in water. Buffer concentration, 0.06-0.2M, examined at various pH values, showed slight effect in the acidic pH range but had no effect in the alkaline region.

THE *Tylophora* group of alkaloids have been shown to possess anticancer activity^{1,2}. In one report inhibition of protein synthesis has been studied with some of these alkaloids³, but their target site and mechanism of action are yet to be determined. Since these alkaloids have drug potential, it is very important to examine the interaction and association of these compounds with biologically active macromolecules, especially proteins and nucleic acids. Such studies would obviously throw light on the mechanism involved in the inhibition of tumour growth, protein synthesis and other biological reactions. We therefore were prompted to undertake such investigations with these alkaloids. Tylophorinidine, the most active alkaloid which has shown significant activity against leukemia-120² was selected for this purpose. During the initial studies it became essential to understand the fluorescence characteristics of this compound in methanol and in aqueous medium under different concentrations of buffer and pH.

Experimental

Tylophorinidine :

Tylophorinidine was isolated and purified in our laboratory according to the new procedure reported earlier⁴. Its structure was established by X-ray method⁵. For the present studies, it was recrystallised from ethanol before use. Ethanol was refluxed with CaO for 3 hrs and then distilled.

Solutions :

All the buffers were made with AnalaR grade sodium dihydrogen phosphate and disodium hydrogen phosphate and stored at 4°. Methanol (spectroscopy grade) was obtained from Merck.

Fluorescence spectroscopy :

Fluorescence spectra were recorded on an Aminco 4-8110 B spectrophotofluorometer fitted with IP 28 photomultiplier tube and Digilog X-Y recorder. A quartz cell, 1 cm light path, holding approximately 4 ml was used for measurements. All spectra were obtained at air-conditioned room temperature using the same concentration of the solution (4 µg/ml). In a separate experiment, fluorescence intensity was examined as a function of tylophorinidine concentration in methanol. A plot of tylophorinidine concentration versus fluorescence intensity gave a straight line between 1-5 µg/ml. The concentration chosen viz. 4 µg/ml, bears a linear relationship with the fluorescence intensity. Oxygen was not excluded.

Results and Discussion

The excitation and fluorescence spectra of tylophorinidine in methanol is shown in Fig. 1. The two spectra appear mirror image of each other as in the case of other organic compounds⁶.

Fig. 1. Excitation and fluorescence emission spectra of tylophorinidine in methanol and in water. (---) methanol; (—) water: (A) Excitation, (B) Fluorescence, excitation at 290 nm.

The fluorescence spectrum is displaced to longer wavelength by 94 nm. It showed a characteristic band maximum at 380 nm, with a second peak at 365 nm and a shoulder at 400 nm. These characteristics of emission and excitation spectra and the emission intensity were nearly retained when the solvent was changed from methanol to water except that the fluorescence maximum was shifted from 380 nm to 375 nm and a broad hump appeared at about 500 nm.

The effect of varying pH, 5-9, was examined in aqueous phosphate buffer. In Fig. 2 are shown two representative sample spectra taken at pH 5.0

Fig. 2. Fluorescence spectra of tylophorinidine, at pH 5.0(A) and pH 7.6(B) in varying molarity of buffer. Excitation wavelength 290 nm.

and 7.6. Tylophorinidine fluoresced maximally at pH 5.0. However, the fluorescence intensity diminished as the pH was increased, but there was no alteration in the overall spectral pattern which remained the same as in water. The shift to a lower wavelength of 5 nm was consistent and reproducible in repeated experiments. The hump at around 480 nm increased in intensity with increasing pH and ionic strength as the phenolic (OH) concentration decreased and phenolate (O⁻) concentration increased.

The decrease in fluorescence intensity at the band maximum 375 nm as a function of pH is shown in Fig. 3. The data followed a typical 'S' form of a titration curve, indicating ionization of the phenolic hydroxyl at C-6. These results,

Fig. 3. Effect of pH and buffer concentration on the relative fluorescence emission at 375 nm.

therefore, showed that tylophorinidine molecule responds to pH changes in a similar way, as has been found for several polyatomic aromatic molecules⁶⁻¹⁰. In case of phenol, it is well established that quenching in alkaline pH occurs due to ionization of the -OH group and that the ionized species is non-fluorescent^{10,11}. Similarly, it was observed with tylophorinidine that 90% of its fluorescence was quenched at pH 8.0. The pKa value of tylophorinidine obtained from the curve was around 6.65, which is much lower than that of phenol (pKa, 9.89)¹². Similar curves (not shown here) were obtained at 365 nm and 400 nm. The pKa value calculated from these curves, was also the same as that at 375 nm.

The effect of buffer concentration, 0.06-0.2M, was also examined at each pH value in the range mentioned above. Increase in buffer concentration decreased the fluorescence intensity to the extent of 5-12 per cent, which showed slight effect on the pKa

value presented in Table 1. Although the pK_a value at 375 nm is not altered significantly, there is a slight decrease in the pK_a value at 365 nm and 400 nm as the buffer concentration is increased. Thus, these results show that increase in buffer concentration promotes ionization, i.e., the hydroxyl of tylophorinidine at C-6 is ionized at lower pH in high concentration of buffer viz. 0.2M, whereas at low buffer concentration 0.06M, ionization occurs at high pH. At higher pH, above 7.6, when the hydroxyl group at C-6 is in the ionized state, (Fig. 4) it is not affected by buffer concentration (Fig. 2).

Fig. 4. Ionization of tylophorinidine.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF BUFFER CONCENTRATION OF pK_a

Buffer concentration M	pK_a		
	360 nm	375 nm	395 nm
0.06	6.65	6.65	6.675
0.1	6.30	6.65	6.50
0.2	6.025	6.525	6.20

It may be mentioned that although a large number of aromatic organic compounds^{6,7,10,13} have been characterized by their fluorescence emission, it is the first time that we report detailed studies on the fluorescence characteristics of the alkaloid tylophorinidine. From the data presented above, it is obvious that the fluorescence characteristics of tylophorinidine cannot only be utilized for the identification purpose of various analogues, but the same can also be employed advantageously for the investigation of the action and involvement

of tylophorinidine in biological and chemical reactions. Thus, tylophorinidine offers the opportunity for examining its interaction with proteins and nucleic acids by the fluorescence technique.

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